

ATF Fuels in Small Modular Reactors: Neutronic Assessment of FeCrAl Alloys in a PWR-SMR

Lucas Chaves¹, Isabella R. Magalhães¹, Samuel Fernandes², Rafael Miró³, Cláudia Pereira^{1,*}

¹Nuclear Engineering Department - Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (UFMG), Ave. Antônio Carlos, Belo Horizonte, Brazil;

²Physics Department - Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (UFMG), Ave. Antônio Carlos, Belo Horizonte, Brazil;

³Instituto Universitario de Seguridad Industrial, Radiofísica y Medioambiental. Universitat Politècnica de València, Camí de Vera, s/n, València, Spain

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ABSTRACT

This study conducted a neutronic evaluation to assess the viability of replacing Zircaloy-4 fuel cladding with Accident Tolerant Fuels candidates (FeCrAl alloys), focusing specifically on implementing a retrofit strategy within the NuScale SMR-iPWR design. The FeCrAl alloy compositions analyzed are: C06M(Fe-81.75 Cr-10 Al-6) C35M(Fe-79.75 Cr-13 Al-5), C36M(Fe-78.75 Cr-13 Al-5), C36MK(Fe-71 Cr-21 Al-5). Models are made based on the NuScale module, replacing Zirc-4 with FeCrAl. To overcome the neutronic penalty, the clad inner radius and the fuel pellet radius were increased. Steady-state analysis was conducted using the MC code SERPENT 2.2, utilizing ENDF/B-VII.1 cross-section data. Neutronic parameters, power distribution, and moderator temperature coefficient (MTC) was assessed. The models with FeCrAl achieved benchmark excess reactivity, respecting the safety MTC limits. The power profile changed due to the decreasing moderator-fuel ratio presented in the FeCrAl models. Overall, the present analysis shows good neutronic feasibility of ATF methods in a SMR design.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Neutronics, SMR, ATF, FeCrAl

1. INTRODUCTION

The Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident in March 2011 was triggered by a major earthquake and subsequent tsunami, resulting in the loss of external power and the subsequent failure of the reactor cooling systems. As decay heat could not be removed, the fuel rods overheated, causing zirconium-vapor reactions that produced hydrogen and resulted in explosions and severe damage to the fuel. This event highlighted the vulnerability of conventional zirconium-based fuel cladding under accident conditions, driving the development of Accident Tolerant Fuels (ATF). ATF concepts aim to enhance fuel and cladding performance during regular operation and in scenarios involving coolant loss by improving oxidation resistance, thermal conductivity, and mechanical stability. FeCrAl alloys have emerged as promising candidates for ATF cladding to mitigate hydrogen generation and maintain integrity under extreme conditions.

FeCrAl alloys present notable thermophysical advantages over Zirconium alloys. FeCrAl typically has a thermal conductivity comparable to that of Zr alloys and slightly higher than that of Zircaloy-4 for Light Water Reactors (LWR) within the normal operating temperature range (500 K to 700 K). Moreover, FeCrAl alloys exhibit a higher specific heat capacity (C_p) than Zircaloy-4 within the operating range [1]. However, FeCrAl claddings are notoriously known to impose a high neutronic penalty on nuclear systems [2-4]. This tendency was anticipated for this work, based on previous studies that used FeCrAl claddings in LWRs [1].

This paper's primary objective is to develop a methodology to overcome the neutron penalty associated with the cladding composition replacement Zr-FeCrAl, as identified in previous work, thereby

*claudia@nuclear.ufmg.br

ensuring maximum retrofitting capacity. In other words, ensure the viability of replacing Zr-based alloys with FeCrAl alloys, with the minimum perturbation possible, in the PWR project, specifically the NuScale design. The authors chose an approach to lower the FeCrAl cladding thickness, based on several articles on the subject [2], [5 - 7]. This evaluation was made using the MC transport nuclear code SERPENT 2.2 [8], using the ENDF/B-VII.1 cross-section data [9].

2. METHODOLOGY

For this work, the authors continue to investigate the following FeCrAl cladding candidates, as presented in Table I, as reported in [10].

Table I. - FeCrAl alloy compositions: weight fractions and mass density at 300K.

	C06M	C35M	C36M	C36MK
Fe-nat [%wf]	0.8175	0.7975	0.7875	0.7100
Cr-nat [%wf]	0.1000	0.1300	0.1300	0.2100
Al-27 [%wf]	0.0600	0.0500	0.0500	0.0500
Mo-nat [%wf]	0.0200	0.0200	0.0200	0.0300
Si-nat [%wf]	0.0020	0.0020	0.0020	0.000
Y-89 [%wf]	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.000
Density [g/cm³]	7.5226	7.5795	7.5007	7.5311

Model verification

The PWR-SMR NuScale module specifications, as per SDA (Standard Design Application) [11], are presented in *Table II*. The design choices for this work use the EURATOM benchmark [12] for design verification. Control rods (CR's) are not modeled in the present analysis. The core model was in equilibrium, and the load conditions are illustrated in *Figure 2* and summarized in *Table III*. The nuclear code used for this evaluation, as well as the cross-section libraries, was the same as those used in the EURATOM benchmark – SERPENT 2.2, utilizing ENDF/B-VII.1. A simulation was made using the same geometry and parameters as those in the Benchmark. The verification results are presented in Section 3. The model used in the simulation is shown in *Figure 1*.

Table II. NuScale design parameters, according to SDA.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Assembly Matrix	17x17	Fuel pellet outer radius	0.406 cm
N° of fuel pins	264	N° of tube guides	24
Fuel pin pitch	1.259 cm	Assembly height	200 cm (active part)
Cladding material	Zircaloy-4/FeCrAl	Assembly pitch	21.503 cm
Zirc-4 Cladding temperature/density	600 K/6.56 g/cm ³	Assembly types	3 (Fresh)
FeCrAl Cladding temperature/density	600 K / 7.5 g/cm ^{3**}	n° of Assemblies	37

Table II (continuation). NuScale design parameters, according to SDA.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Cladding outer radius	0.475 cm	N ^o of UOX+Gd pins per assembly	16*
Fuel gap material	He	Gadolinium concentration	6%*
Fuel gap temperature	600 K	Radial reflector material	SS304
Fuel gap outer radius	0.414 cm	Radial reflector Thickness	7.62 cm
Fuel pellet	UO _x / UO _x + Gd	Coolant/moderator	Water
Fuel enrichment (UO _x)	2.6% ~ 4.55%	Coolant temperature	600 K
Fuel temp.	900 K	Core Thermal Output	160Wth

*The number of Gd bars for this model was defined by the EURATOM design and verified by the authors in a parallel evaluation [13]. ** The mean density of 7.5 g/cm³ was considered for all FeCrAl materials for this simulation. The corrected density of FeCrAl materials at 600K can be checked on [1]

Figure 1. Left to right, respectively: Radial plot (active section) / Axial plot (middle section) of NuScale-like core in equilibrium state. SERPENT 2.2.1 - generated image by the authors.

Figure 2. NuScale Loading Pattern for Reference Equilibrium Cycle.

Table III. - Assembly types and the assembly enrichment, according to [11].

Assembly types	Enrichment	Assembly types	Enrichment
A-1	1.50 wt% U-235	C-1	4.05 wt% U-235
A-2	1.60 wt% U-235	C-2	4.55 wt% U-235 + 16 pins Gd ₂ O ₃
B-1	2.50 wt% U-235	C-3	2.60 wt% U-235
B-2	2.60 wt% U-235		

After verifying the author's model, adjustments were made to the simulation parameters and geometry. The first change was to the neutrons and the cycle/batch numbers. The Benchmark uses 1E6 neutrons for 2500 active cycles, skipping the first 200. For computational availability, the authors analyzed the model convergence, multiplication factor, and entropy-wise. Running parameter values for maximum convergence and lower computational cost, without compromising sensitivity, were found using 300,000 neutrons, 300 active cycles, and skipping 200 cycles (500 cycles total). Spacer grids were not used in this evaluation. The removal of spacer grids does not compromise reactor sensitivity, as expected, since the spacers have a minimal impact on neutronics. The verified model's effective multiplication factor (k -eff), referred to as the STANDARD model (STD) from now on, is presented in Section 3.

Cladding Design

This work proposes a model with some structural and neutronic retrofit capacity (decrease cladding thickness without changing the water channels, fuel rod length, fuel rod base structures, etc.). That premise requires the same excess reactivity, maintaining the same reactivity control properties/values (gadolinium rods + boron curve). Maintain these characteristic demands by increasing the inner radius of the cladding and the fuel pellet radius, while maintaining the gap thickness. This scenario seems to be a more reasonable choice compared with other works [6][7]. Maintaining the gap thickness is critical to ensure the model's thermal features and to minimize the neutron penalty due to gap increase and the inherent FeCrAl penalty [2]. More details about this scenario choice are covered in the results section. The k -eff for all cases is presented in Section 3.

To perform the analysis, 2 model types are proposed:

MODEL TYPE A, following the strategy to replace the ~0.60 mm thick Zr alloy cladding types with 0.35 mm thick FeCrAl alloy cladding, adjusting the UO_x content, maintaining the Low Enriched Uranium (LEU) project proposal [14].

MODEL TYPE B, using 0.45 mm thick FeCrAl alloys, and High-Assay Low-Enriched Uranium (HALEU) or LEU+ (enr. < 10% U-235) fuel type, to overcome the neutron penalty. 0.45 mm thick FeCrAl alloys exhibit enhanced mechanical strength compared to 0.725 mm PWR zircaloy tubes [2].

The optimal fuel enrichment in MODELS TYPE A and B was defined heuristically, increasing the enrichment proportionally, until the k -eff matches the BENCHMARK core k -eff with an error less than 100 pcm, for all 8 models. The core models made for the present evaluation are summarized in *Table IV*.

Table IV. Model types and enrichment range.

MODEL TYPE A	Enrichment range	MODEL TYPE B	Enrichment range
A-C06M	1.90% ~ 4.95%	B-C06M	2.10% ~ 5.15%
A-C35M	1.90% ~ 4.95%	B-C35M	2.10% ~ 5.15%
A-C36M	1.90% ~ 4.95%	B-C36M	2.10% ~ 5.15%
A-C36MK	1.92% ~ 4.97%	B-C36MK	2.13% ~ 5.18%

Steady State Evaluation

A steady-state evaluation was conducted for the 8 FeCrAl models and the STD model. The boundary conditions are set as 'black' (neutrons can escape the model). In steady-state evaluation, the core flux spectra, leak rate, core total flux, and radial power distribution were assessed.

For the moderator temperature coefficient (MTC) evaluation, a batch of simulations was made for each model, changing the average moderator temperature. The temperature range chosen for this evaluation is provided in the SDA. The MTC was calculated using the following equation:

$$MTC_i = \frac{\rho_i - \rho_{ref}}{T_i - T_{ref}}, \text{ where: } \rho = (k_{eff} - 1)/k_{eff}.$$

The “ref” values here are the first (coldest) temperature/ k -eff evaluated, and $\Delta T = T_i - T_{ref}$. The derivatives method was used to propagate the MTC error. The error σ_{MTC} linked to each MTC value will be:

$$\sigma_{MTC,i} [pcm/^\circ F] = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_{\rho_i}^2 + \sigma_{\rho_{ref}}^2}}{\Delta T} \times 10^5, \text{ and are present in the results in the MTC box chart graph.}$$

3. RESULTS

The effective multiplication factor for model verification is shown in *Table V*. The absolute difference between the STANDARD Model and the Benchmark is less than 100 pcm, which retains sufficient sensitivity to verify and compare the model with other works verified by the same reference benchmark. *Figure 3* compares the relative power distribution (STD and Benchmark). The STD overall power distribution is preserved, compared to the reference.

Table V. k-eff comparison between Benchmark and author's models.

MODEL	k-eff	Computational error (σ) [pcm]
EURATOM – Benchmark	1.02768	1
AUTHORS Verification	1.02778	2.5
STANDARD MODEL (STD)*	1.02855	13

* Reduced neutrons/cycle history. Model without Spacer grids. Absolute difference between STD and Benchmark model: 87 pcm.

Figure 3. Global Relative Power Distribution - EURATOM Benchmark (right), STD model (left). Maximum power deviation (position): 2,6. Absolute difference: 0.92%

Table VI shows the neutronics and the peak factor F_q for the models. The B MODEL TYPES (0.45mm FeCrAl cladding) have a similar behavior to the standard model, flux-wise, and a lower leak rate compared to the MODELS A and the STD model, a good feature for SMR design. All FeCrAl models concentrate their peak factor at the reactor center. This behavior can lead to an irradiation stress in the assembly C-3. The A MODEL TYPES have their peak factor values more comparable with the STD

model. Figure 5 represents the flux spectra as a function of energy for the different models. A weaker flux is observed in the epithermal region of the figure. (energy $< \sim 10^{-6}$ MeV) for all FeCrAl models. This behavior can be attributed to the high absorption cross section in the thermal region of FeCrAl alloys [1].

Table VI. Effective multiplication factor, total flux, and leak rate for all models - steady state evaluation.

MODELS	k-eff	TOTAL FLUX [1/cm ² .s]	TOTAL LEAK RATE [1/s]	Peak Factor F _q	Position
STD	1.02855	2.82031E+18	1.125E+15	1.1736	6,5
A-C06M	1.02831	3.00245E+18	1.194E+15	1.1871	4,4
A-C35M	1.02736	3.00619E+18	1.196E+15	1.1880	4,4
A-C36M	1.02726	3.00597E+18	1.195E+15	1.1888	4,4
A-C36MK	1.02774	3.00157E+18	1.195E+15	1.1868	4,4
B-C06M	1.02833	2.86504E+18	1.112E+15	1.2327	4,4
B-C35M	1.02695	2.86880E+18	1.116E+15	1.2349	4,4
B-C36M	1.02722	2.86948E+18	1.116E+15	1.2312	4,4
B-C36MK	1.02762	2.86261E+18	1.113E+15	1.2400	4,4
σ (mean):	0.00012	1.30000E-04**	8.500E-04**	0.0025*	N/A

* Mean of $\pm 2\sigma$ uncertainty: $mean(value(i,j)*computational\ error(i,j)*2)$. **Errors \ll significant digits, it can be neglected.

The MTC for MODELS TYPE A and B can be seen in Figure 4. The results are presented in Fahrenheit to match the SDA curve, facilitating future analysis/consultations. All the MODELS respect the maximum MTC allowed in the project. Besides that, positive feedback can raise safety concerns. Model A-C06M, B-C06M, and B-C35M have a negative MTC through the batches. The other models begin with the MTC with positive feedback, going negative as the temperature rises. An MTC with a negative feedback range assures stable and self-regulating reactor behavior, where power increases naturally lead to a compensatory decrease in reactivity, keeping safe operation.

Figure 4. Left: MTC for the TYPE A MODELS. Right: MTC for TYPE B MODELS.

Figure 5. Flux spectra for all models - steady state

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

Detailed neutronic evaluations using the SERPENT 2.2 Monte Carlo code were assessed in this work, analyzing four distinct FeCrAl alloys: C06M, C35M, C36M, and C36MK (Kanthal APMT). The central challenge addressed was overcoming the inherent neutronic penalty associated with FeCrAl, which has a significantly larger thermal-neutron absorption cross-section than Zircaloy. This penalty was bypassed primarily by investigating reduced cladding thicknesses (0.35 mm and 0.45 mm) and adjusting enrichment levels and pellet geometry, respecting the retrofit capability.

A steady-state analysis was conducted to assess the neutronics, power distribution, and the moderator temperature coefficient. The results show promising agreement with the project parameters. The most impactful difference can be shown in the peak factors. The FeCrAl B MODELS have higher relative power than the STD or reference models. Increasing the fuel pellet disturbs the moderator/Fuel ratio. The ratio changes, altering the fuel pellet radius, which can lead to a perturbation in the probability of resonance escape and directly increases the reactor's volumetric energy (q'').

The results indicate that cladding replacement can be feasible in a neutronically feasible retrofit scenario. For the retrofit approach, some additional assessment need to be done to robust this idea, which will be aim for the following works, such as: assessment of moderator and fuel coefficient and control rod worth, checking is the values respects the project safety limits; steady state analysis using the radial power distribution for an approximate temperature distribution; A full burnup analysis; A more robust transient analysis utilizing nodal time dependent codes or/and coupled physics (neutronic-thermohydraulic). It is also valid to consider other approaches besides retrofit to achieve a more optimal fuel-gap-cladding thickness that respects the original design basis power production/distribution profile. It is essential to note that the retrofit approach often falls short of the original designs, particularly due to the inherent nature of FeCrAl neutron economics. Still, the FeCrAl usage in existing projects has significant potential to improve ATF performance, offering superior mechanical strength and orders of magnitude greater resistance to creep, as well as superior oxidation resistance at high temperatures, leading to better performance in accident conditions.

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